

A Study of Symbiotic Relationship Between Media Responsibility and Media Ethics.

"Let noble thoughts come to us from every side." Rigveda

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Abstract:

Today, we witness the colossal role of media in the context of changing democratic values. Are media people exercising trustworthiness, honesty, accountability, and self-restraint while reporting? The media is the tool for shaping public opinion. But while discharging duties, the media has to follow certain moral standards of behaviour. For vibrant and healthy democracy, media acts like a bridge between public and politicians. Sanjaya who was blessed with an inner eye to report and narrate the events of the battlefield of Kurukshetra. This print culture has become obsolete with the invasion of internet. It has been replaced by digital media, since it is cheaper and easy to produce and distribute. The present research will examine the functions of media in nation building. Thomas Carlyle referred the press as the 'Fourth Estate of the Realm'. Ethics formulates ethical theories or principles under which individual human actions are evaluated as right or wrong. Citizen journalism is growing now. Most people are now using smart mobile phones. Videos and stills taken can directly be sent to the news desks of broadcasters. This has given rise to cyberbullying, unlawful harassment, and breach of another person's privacy. The internet has changed journalism. The political system mired by cancerous corruption and decline in the ethical values had changed the media scenario. Media was at the forefront when terrorists targeted innocent civilians in Mumbai. At this juncture, it is expected that media should report the information without resorting sensationalism. Media have an immense responsibility of fighting issues like casteism, communalism and corruption and helping people to come out of poverty and other

social evils. For this, having media ethics in place becomes extremely important. Findings of this paper would be based on core media ethics like objectivity and fairness, restrained and socially acceptable language, transparency, impartiality, accountability, probity and integrity are important for maintaining and sustaining certain ethical standards of news. Media needs to be extra-cautious while collecting and disseminating information.

Key Words: Media, Sensationalism, Information, Transparency, Language, Ethics, Responsibility, Integrity.

Introduction:

Today, we can witness the colossal role of media in the context of changing democratic values. Are media people exercising trustworthiness, honesty, accountability, and self-restraint while reporting? The role of media has always remained sceptical, as media men failed to promote the media ethics. In today's situation even a child can say that media professionals and journalists report erroneous and false paid news. Media professionals are not fair enough while reporting and analysing news of public interest. All these people, consciously or unconsciously, fail to understand ethics and ethical standards of journalism. Obviously, they must play significant role in investigating and exposing corporate and political scandals and the wrongdoings of politicians and bureaucrats. But while discharging duties, the media has to follow certain moral standards of behaviour. For vibrant and healthy democracy, media acts like a bridge between public and politicians. In this paper, we examine the role of media in relation to changing technology and socio-political situations.

The true function of media is to show naked truth and bitter realities of the socio-political life. Traditional media has made a perfect sense by following media ethics. Obviously, some of the cases unearthed by media are commendable. But now days, conventional media is disrupted by advancement of technology. Due to drastic changes in information and communication technology, there are major impediments in adhering to standard ethical codes. There is a great danger to the society if media works unprofessionally. It can be a cause of major source of conflict and can create a rift between different religious and ethnic groups. Political interference, amendments of laws time to time, importance given self-preservation and self-expansion, mercenary motives are some of the major challenges in ensuing media ethics. Technology has transformed once big and far world into tiny global village. Thanks to technology, we now have power to communicate with anybody anywhere at any time in the world.

Hypothesis: Media ethics is not a gut feeling of right or wrong but there exists a symbiotic relationship between media ethics and media responsibility.

Objectives of Study:

1. To understand the concepts like Media and Ethics.
2. To know the symbiotic relationship between ethics and media responsibilities.
3. To explore the significance of media ethics in the context of technology.

Research Methodology:

The descriptive methodology is used for this research study. The secondary data is collected from websites, journals, books and research papers and articles.

Literature Review:

A Historical Perspective:

First Printing press invented by Caxton (1475 or 1476) democratised values and changed the very nature of print culture. It is credited for spreading religion, politics and science. Print culture revolutionised the society and people got an access to information and opened new vistas to express their opinions freely and candidly.

Sanjaya who was blessed with an inner eye to report and narrate the events of the battlefield of Kurukshetra. If modern media channels are given the task of Sanjaya, they would add their views and masala to increase the TRP and create hype and fear among the viewers. The TRP has become matter of power and position for the channels, and they are ready to go to any extent for that. They would do everything to increase the popularity and we too rely on them and fall prey to their half-baked truth. Therefore, the point here is to be noted that media professionals have an enormous and onerous task of upholding the social and democratic values of the society for safeguarding freedom of information. This print culture has become obsolete with the invasion of internet. It has been replaced by digital media since it is cheaper and easy to produce and distribute. Undoubtedly, people expect from media to follow certain ethical standards. Ethical, objective reporting, and quest for truth are the essential attributes of mass media.

Sanjaya is very subtle and sublime example of transparent journalism in Indian mythology. He narrates the activities to the blind king morally and with honesty. He is not hesitant of reporting deaths of his king's son at the hands of Pandava brothers. Today's blindfolded viewers are like a Dhritarashtra, who is eager to know the exciting and exotic news to excite their imagination. Sanjay often seems to report the controversial happenings of Kurukshetra, but he does not report it controversially. As far as media ethics are concerned, true media professions seek truth, as truth ultimately prevails, secondly creation of good faith among the viewers/readers, thirdly minimising harm and last but not the least, acting independently but with full accountability. They need to act according to their conscience and with pure awareness for professional judgment. A media is a watchdog and has the potential to put any government on tenterhook and can even topple corrupt government. But if the media becomes financially dependent on political parties or business houses, it loses its lustre and freedom to function independently. This very fact changes its loyalty towards political parties and not towards common people.

Samuel Pepys, a celebrated diarist reported honestly and sincerely three major events of the seventeenth century namely The Great Plague (1665), The Great Fire of London (1666) and a Naval War against the Dutch. He was totally engrossed in the idiosyncratic imagery of the London of his time. It sounds like our own experiences of the 2020 Covid-19 Pandemic. He provides a valuable insight to us though his candid and truthful accounts of what happened during the seventeenth century England. He also shows undoubtedly the political, social and political picture of life of that period. He describes what he observed and experienced in his life.

Forgoing discussion points out objective journalism which is absent today. False representation of facts is the upshot of subjective journalism which affects the overall perception and views of people. Biased news coverage leads the fabrication and manipulation of truth. Sensualisation and sensationalism of news coverage, trial by media eroding the public trust, despite stringent guidelines issued by the Supreme court. Media power has grown exponentially due to technological changes and social media. The amount of information is doubling every year.

The vital idea that needs to be taken care of is moral sensitivity while dealing seriously regarded subjects. We are utterly shattered at the time of news of massacre and the resultant photography. All media houses have been transformed into commercial hubs. It is also a

justifiable fear that the picture shown by media is so misrepresented, distorted and twisted that it becomes harmful and detrimental for the overall health of the society. Media plays significant role in good governance. Democracy without dissent is a meaningless concept, as public disagreement becomes a creative force. Raymond Snoddy has very succinctly put it, “a full flow of information is essential in a democracy if citizens are to make informed judgements and will also make government more efficient through all policy options being discussed fully before a choice is made.” (R. Snoddy, *The good, the bad and the unacceptable*, p.172.)

Discussion

However, in democratic set-up, media houses, no longer play a fair role. A free media is no longer a potential voice of dissent. What we find today is major media houses are run by either political parties or big business houses. Arguably, a freedom of speech is the most precious thing of democracy. Therefore, the free press has the right to safeguard the democratic rights of the people. In the history of the civilisations, only conscientious objectors could write the history. Enlightened and vigilant media is the only guarantee for a smooth functioning of democracy.

Thomas Carlyle referred the press as the ‘Fourth Estate of the Realm’. For vibrant and exuberant democracy, mass media plays a significant role, as it presents truthful, accurate, objective, and fair news. It keeps the people informed and facilitates public debate. Obviously, their sole aim is: give and take- to sell the news and make a profit. It is needless to say that these media houses serve the interests of the shareholders-not of common people. It is not a surprising fact that their sole aim is not only to satisfy political bosses but to actively advance their agenda to further political ambitions. In the morning, compulsive reading of newspapers only gives us the news about unedifying accounts of political manoeuvring, rapes, mass murders which only develop a preference for sensationalism and gratification of baser instincts. Print media or social media conveniently forgets to enhance one’s general awareness and equip the young minds for the battle called life. An ulterior motive is of media is just entertainment.

It is a branch of philosophy in which we study about human actions, attitudes, and behaviours as good or bad, or right or wrong. Ethics formulates ethical theories or principles under which individual human actions are evaluated as right or wrong. It is also called a moral philosophy.

Ethics has its roots in Latin 'ethicus' and the Greek 'ethikos' which mean characters or manners. An ethical journalists strive to ensure free and accurate information, which is fair and thorough, since he verifies it before releasing. He does not falsify or suppress essential information. He is abided by the same high moral standards as he expects of others. He avoids prejudicial or pejorative reference to an individual's religion, colour, physical or mental illness, unless genuinely relevant to the story.

Citizen journalism is growing now. Most people are now using smart mobile phones. Videos and stills taken can directly be sent to the news desks of broadcasters. This has given rise to cyberbullying, unlawful harassment, and breach of another person's privacy. All broadcasters accept such news without knowing veracity of it. There are genuine concerns about the ethics of such video. Videos of Mumbai bomb blast or deadliest terror attacks, alert passengers could video-shoot and photographed these events and sent it to the news-desk. This was possible because of ever changing technology. The internet has changed journalism. It has been an incredible power tool providing instant information. News desk reporters instantly get news. Some people take undue advantage and use it as an opportunity to attack and malign the people without fact checking.

Media are influential so they abound and circulate knowledges and viewpoints. Whether in cities or remote villages, even when people do not actively seek them out, they are approached by different forms of communications. Media are universal, more readily retrieved via a variability of platforms. Current democratization of media means people other than professional media operatives are actively involved in content creation and distribution. (Esan, 2016)

Today's dismal picture of contemporary media compels us to think of content, language and style of media. It can be easily gauged that fourth estate had maintained a certain ethical standard during the first four decades of the post independent era. The internet has brought the remarkable changes in the way that media people work and in the way the media industry is being shaped. The political system mired by cancerous corruption and decline in the ethical values had changed the media scenario.

Media was at the forefront when terrorists targeted innocent civilians in Mumbai. At this juncture, it is expected that media should report the information without resorting sensationalism. To calm the public and maintaining integrity and secrecy of information, the

authority requests for refrain from making news sensitive. At this juncture, the reporting task becomes arduous. During these challenging moments, coverage of entire terrorist's event reveals the role of media within society. The whole reporting is done like a gradual development of tragic plot of a mysterious novel, violence, surprise, action and climax. In these cases, powerful image of the institution of media is being shattered on the commercial front. Consequently, reportage of such sensitive news is observed as a parochial and is wrongly perceived and received by the public.

Information is power now, not knowledge. In democratic set-up like India, spread of information is of prime importance for the smooth functioning of the democracy. Media plays the role of informer and seeks to strike a balance between government and public. Popularly known as mass media, it is being liberalised, globalised, privatised, and most importantly commercialised with the hope that democratic values can be deeply rooted in the public sphere. Mass media is quite helpful in the process of strengthening and deepening the roots of democracy. (Oso, 2012).

Today, the need to regulate electronic media content and sensibilisation of news was felt during emergencies. The government too agreed to respect the freedom of press and abstained from stringent regulatory measures; however, the News Broadcasters Association created a code of ethics to be followed during the time of emergencies. It indicates violation of ethical standards by media. The television channels had wider coverage and were available on prominent social media sites. Live feeds were also made available for public viewing.

There is a need to study and calculate the advertisement revenue collected by the national channels at the time of live telecast during emergency situations. Quantitative analysis needs to be done in this regard. The commercial viability of the live feeding of the advertisement sponsorship is more during the time of emergencies. It has blatantly violated the ethical standards of media ethics. The coverage of the 26/11 terror attacks is the case in study. The way the print media gave the news feeds to the world is praiseworthy. It followed the media ethics like truthfulness, accuracy, transparency etc, but TV reporters for TV channels, haphazardly prepared the news without appropriate facts, gave news only to create sensation and fear in the minds of public for improving TRP rates. (Neelamalar, Chitra and Darwin, 2009).

Today, media has become a very powerful and amazing tool for influencing public opinion. Media ethics espouses the moral philosophy of society, as it happens to be honest and open communication. Basic media ethics that right thing should be done. Concisely, ethics has multifaceted area and calls for basic aspects of media practice. Media correspondents should carry out stories that would ensure truth and accuracy and stop victimising the victims. Explicitly, it should provide moral background to the society. It should hold moral standards at all the times. While generating and collecting profits, every aspect moral and ethical standard should be maintained. Another important underlying function of media is to instil cultural values.

Systematic attempts have been made to jeopardize the information and privacy features of the media. Public authorities and political parties through mass media started manipulating people by propaganda and disinformation. These authorities may have found threat or danger to their existence. The greatest merit or in some cases demerit of social media is speedy transmission of information. Media can become a prey to commercial interests and to the pressure of certain political parties.

Technology comes in handy in facilitating smooth communication among individuals or businesses, as it provides alternatives that lead to effective communication. Over the past period, technology has altered the methods that human beings use to communicate. Communication and technological development have gone together in the entire history, and the emergence of mobile and internet services have propelled communication to exceptionally high levels. The introduction of internet and the option of chatting and sending emails are probably the most noteworthy influence of technology on media. Communication quality has significantly improved due to availability and accessibility of helpful knowledge in various websites.

There are various ways of communication the utilize technology and they include email, blogs, video calls, cellular phones, and online chats. Technology has a cons impact on the development of interpersonal skills and should be avoided in cases where such skills require being nurtured. On the same side, the same rule should apply when communicating with people who do not understand how certain communication gadgets operate. Further, there are cases of disabled individuals who cannot perceive advanced communication gadgets, but simple visual signs.

Nevertheless, technology is very beneficial to all our lives, and we cannot go backwards in time once we have already advanced forward in motion for a more. But to conserve how much we lean on technology and devices to carry us through our lives can be limited or exercised to a degree of discipline away from it. The Internet has increased the amount of communication globally, yet ironically the very technology that helps us increase our communication hinders our ability to socialize effectively in real life and create a healthy interpersonal relationship.

Conclusion: Media have an immense responsibility of fighting issues like casteism, communalism and corruption and helping people to come out of poverty and other social evils. For this, having media ethics in place becomes extremely important. Core media ethics like objectivity and fairness, restrained and socially acceptable language, transparency, impartiality, accountability, probity, and integrity are important for maintaining and sustaining certain ethical standards of news. Media must be extra-cautious while collecting and disseminating information. The vital task for media is not the fabrication and distortion of truth, but to advance harmony and peace. It should not propagate malicious information that would disrupt and torment others. A true journalist is accountable, objective, truthful and courageous and most important vigilant. He should detach himself from immoral act of sponsoring paid news.

Scope for further study:

However, there is further scope for study in the formation of international code of ethics for media which would be followed with letter and spirit irrespective of cultural and economic differences.

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